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PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system for the thermal management of an LTO cell for high-current profiles

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the concept of a passive thermal management system (TMS), including natural convection, heat pipe, and phase change material (PCM) for electric vehicles. Experimental and numerical tests are described to predict the thermal behavior of a lithium-titanate (LTO) battery cell in a high current discharging process. Details of various thermal management techniques are discussed and compared with each other. The mathematical models are solved by COMSOL Multiphysics®, the commercial computational fluid dynamics (CFD) software. The simulation results are validated against experimental data with an acceptable error range. Results indicate that the maximum cell temperature for the cooling strategies of natural convection, heat pipe, and PCM assisted heat pipe reaches 56 °C, 46.3 °C, and 33.2 °C, respectively. It is found that the maximum cell temperature experienced a 17.3% and 40.7% reduction by heat pipe and PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system compared with natural convection.

1. Introduction

In the last decades, electric vehicles have been received more attention owing to their environmentally-friendly features. The battery is known as the main energy source for electric vehicles. Lithium-ion (Li-ion) batteries are the most favorable ones among all kinds of batteries, because of their stable performance, long cycle life, low self-discharge, and high specific energy features [1,2]. However, their performance and life span are highly temperature-dependent and limited by their operating condition [3–6]. Therefore, it is essential to build and design an applied and highly effective battery thermal management system (TMS) to control the cell temperature, especially at high C-rates. Generally, C-rate is the rate of charging/discharging of the cell concerning its maximum capacity. The best operational temperature for Li-ion batteries is in the range of between 25 °C to 40 °C [7,8]. Thus, some cooling strategies in the form of active, passive, and hybrid are inspected to meet the heat dissipation requirement of the Li-ion batteries. Active cooling systems require an external source of energy and are classified into forced air and liquid cooling systems [9]. Conversely, passive cooling systems, comprising phase change materials (PCMs), heat pipes, fins, and natural convection do not consume any

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Nomenclature

Δt	Time Interval (t)
T	Battery Temperature (K)
I	Discharge Current (Ah)
V	Operating Voltage (V)
m	Mass of the Cell (kg)
c_p	Specific Heat Capacity (J/kg.K)
T_{amb}	Ambient Temperature (K)
R_{bt}	Total Resistance of the Battery (K/W)
R_{tab}	Total Resistance of the Battery Tab (K/W)
k	Thermal Conductivity (W/m.K)
p	Pressure (Pa)
S	Cross-section of the Tab and Cell (m ²)
h	Heat Transfer Coefficient (W/m ² .K)
q_{conv}	Free Cooling Heat Transfer (W)
Q_{Cell}	Power Loss of Battery (W)
g_i	Gravity (m/s ²)
q_g	Cell Heat Generation (W)
V	Volume (m ³)
H	Height (m)
T_m	Melting Temperature of the PCM (K)
u	Velocity (m/s)
s	Solid Phase of PCM
l	Liquid Phase of PCM

Greek

ρ	Density (kg/m ³)
ρ'	Resistivity (K/W)

Acronyms

CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
TMS	Thermal Management System
NC	Natural Convection
LTO	Lithium-titanate
HP	Heat Pipe
SOC	State of Charge
Li-ion	Lithium-ion
PCM	Phase Change Material

external energy [10]. Hybrid cooling systems can be a combination of passive, active, or both of them [11].

Forced air cooling is known as the simplest TMS owing to the low engineering cost, simple design requirements, and high adaptability. Many studies experimentally and numerically investigate the effect of air-cooling on battery thermal management [12–15]. Despite the active cooling system, air cooling is not a successful cooling method in emergency conditions, high charge-discharge C-rates, and hot climate due to the low heat transfer coefficient of the air [16,17].

The liquid cooling system is the most promising cooling system which is applied in the electric vehicle industry [18–20]. Owing to the high heat transfer coefficient of the liquids, it can effectively remove the heat from the battery module/pack [21,22]. However, the liquid cooling systems are heavy and need high investment cost, high power, and require space. They also have leakage and high-pressure drop problems [23].

PCMs are one of the universal passive methods which are common in many cooling and energy storage applications in recent years [24–26]. PCM is a substance that can store/release a huge amount of energy in the solid-liquid transformation process and at a constant temperature [27]. PCMs benefit from the simple layout and no power consumption that could effectively decrease the maximum temperature rise of the battery in the normal working condition. However, most PCMs suffers from the low thermal conductivity and leaking problem after the melting process [28–30]. Therefore, a number of methods like adding nanoparticles, fins, meshes, and heat pipes are used to compensate for these issues [31–37].

Heat pipes are known as phase-change heat transfer devices which can be used in many cooling applications because of their high heat transfer ability, low cost, low maintenance, and high lifetime [38,39]. When the heat pipe is heated in the evaporator section, the working fluid inside the heat pipe evaporates and changes to vapor form. Due to increasing the pressure, the vapor moves to the condenser section, where the vapor fluid condenses and releases the heat into the ambient. The condensed working fluid returns to the

evaporator section in the wick structure by capillary force [40]. As the condenser section of the heat pipe must always be cooled, the heat pipe cooling method needs a second cooling system as its condenser. Therefore, it is classified as a hybrid cooling system. Many researchers have studied the combination of the heat pipe battery TMS with a secondary active cooling system. Behi et al. [41] experimentally and numerically considered the effect of the flat heat pipe-based air cooling system on the cylindrical battery module at a 1.5C discharging rate. Feng et al. [42] experimentally investigated the cooling performance of the air-cooled heat pipe cooling device for a cylindrical battery pack. Behi et al. [43] experimentally and numerically analyzed the cooling performance of the flat heat pipe combined liquid and air cooling systems for the high current discharging (8C). Zhao et al. [44] designed a mature cooling technology using flat heat pipe, air cooling, and wet cooling in the 3C discharging rate for the prismatic battery pack. A combination of the heat pipe as a superconductor with PCM as a secondary condenser and energy storage is a common method in battery cooling applications. In this method, PCM and heat pipes act together to take the heat from the battery into the surrounding air. Zhang et al. [45] experimentally designed a novel heat pipe-assisted PCM cooling system for the prismatic battery pack. They found the proposed system offers a suitable cooling performance for different discharging rates. Jiang and Qu [46] numerically studied the effect of heat pipe and PCM for Li-ion batteries during the discharge-charge cycle. They considered the effect of ambient temperature, PCM melting point, and heat transfer coefficient at the heat pipe condensation section. Huang et al. [47] experimentally investigated the cooling performance of the heat pipe-assisted PCM for the cylindrical battery pack. They found the proposed cooling system had a significant controlling temperature capacity on the battery pack during the 3C discharging rate.

According to the mentioned studies, the following observation can be consequent: (1) Most of the studies for thermal management of the high current applications are active cooling systems. (2) A very few studies are available for the combination of the heat pipe and PCM in high C-rates. To the best of the authors' knowledge, the passive thermal management analysis for Li-ion batteries has been rarely addressed in fast discharging. In this study, a submerged PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system is designed experimentally and numerically for lithium-titanate (LTO) battery cell under fast discharging (8C). We decreased the thermal contact resistance in current cooling systems by direct submerging which leads to higher cooling performance. Moreover, a multizone analysis, using thermal imaging is done for a smarter design to achieve more efficient cooling performance. The current study is organized as follows. Section 2 represents the experimental setup and results. The battery thermal model, validation, and simulation results are described in Section 3. Finally, a relevant conclusion is drawn in Section 4.

2. Experimental setup

2.1. Description of the materials

The experimental setup is built to investigate the performance of the PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system for the thermal management of the LTO battery cell in fast discharging. In this study, a flat heat pipe with distilled water as a working fluid is selected for the thermal management of the battery cell. Generally, heat pipes equipped with water benefit from lower thermal resistance compared with methanol heat pipes. In addition, they are more adaptable for the temperature operation of the batteries [43]. The flat heat pipes are more suitable for thermal management applications due to lower thermal contact resistance. Table 1 presents the main parameters of the flat heat pipe.

The LTO 23 Ah cell has been selected for the experimental tests. The LTO cell is discharged with a high constant current of 184 A from 100% to 0% of the state of charge (SOC). The key parameters of the prismatic LTO cell are shown in Table 2, while Fig. 1 shows the picture of the cell and heat pipe with their dimensions.

2.2. Description of the test setup

In the current study, the cooling performance of the heat pipe has been investigated on the LTO prismatic Li-ion cell in presence of the natural convection and PCM. The picture of the test setup is displayed in Fig. 2. The experimental test setup comprised a PEC battery tester, six flat heat pipes, a prismatic cell, a Pico USB TC-08 data logger, four K-type thermocouples, a thermal camera, and a personal computer. The thermocouples with the accuracy of ± 0.2 °C measured the surface temperature of the LTO cell.

In order to conduct the experiments, the PEC battery tester is used for the cycling of the LTO cell. A personal computer is connected to the data logger to record the cell temperature. The voltage and current of the cell are being monitored by the tester during the

Table 1
The main properties of the heat pipe.

Parameter	Value
Heat pipe length (mm)	250
Dimension L × W (mm)	11.2 × 3.5
Working fluid	Distilled water
Wick structure	Sintered
Thermal conductivity (W/m.K)	8212
Cooling Power (W)	100
Operation temperature (°C)	30–120
Cross-section area (mm ²)	38.32
l_{eff} (mm)	125

Table 2
The main properties of the cell.

Parameter	Value
Chemistry	LTO
Shape	Prismatic
Nominal Voltage (V)	2.3
Maximum voltage (V)	2.7
Minimum voltage (V)	1.5
Capacity (Ah)	23
Specific Energy (J/kg)	96
Energy Density (J/m)	202
Weight (kg)	0.550
Volume (L)	0.260
Dimensions L × W × H (mm)	115 × 22 × 103
Heat specific capacity (J/kg.K)	1150
Thermal conductivity x,y,z (W/m.K)	31, 0.8, 31

Fig. 1. The LTO prismatic cell and heat pipe with their dimensions.

cycling. After connecting the cell to the data logger, and connecting the voltage and current cables, the cell will be charged/discharged. The battery is fully discharged (8C) in 446 sec to reach the lower operating voltage. By charging/discharging the cell, voltage, and current, as well as the resistance of the battery, are characterized. The heat generation of the cell is calculated by Palas and Newman [48], where it is expressed as follows:

$$mC_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + q_{conv} = k_x \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + k_y \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} + k_z \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial z^2} + q_g \quad (1)$$

where m , c_p , T , k , and q_g represent the mass, heat capacity, temperature, thermal conductivity, and heat generation of the cell, respectively. The uncertainties can be calculated according to Schultz and Cole [49,50] as follows:

$$U_R = \left[\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\partial R}{\partial V_i} U_{V_i} \right)^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where U_{V_i} and U_R are the error of each factor and total errors, respectively. Table 3 shows the measurement correctness of each factor. The maximum uncertainty is less than 2.01%.

2.3. Experimental results and discussion

2.3.1. Performance of the natural convection on LTO cell

The natural convection cooling system is the first and simplest cooling method that expresses a specific case compared with the forced convection cooling when the inlet air velocity is zero. The goal of natural convection cooling is to find out the outcome of the LTO cell heat generation on the transient thermal characteristics of the cell during the 8C discharging process. This result can deliver precise guidance to compare the cell temperature with or without TMS. Fig. 3 shows the location of the thermocouples, the

Fig. 2. The picture of the experimental system. (1) prismatic cell embedded with heat pipes; (2) data logger and thermocouples; (3) PEC® battery tester (4) thermal Camera and; (5) personal computer.

Table 3

The uncertainties of the experimental parameters.

Parameter	Uncertainty
Current (A)	$\pm 0.005\%$
Voltage (V)	$\pm 0.005\%$
Thermocouple ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	± 0.2
Data logger ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	± 0.025

temperature curves, and the infrared image of the cell at a discharging regime of 8C under natural convection. As can be seen, the temperature trend of the thermocouples is almost the same. However, the thermocouples of T_1 and T_4 experienced higher temperatures compared with the T_2 and T_3 . This LTO cell cannot be efficiently cooled down due to the low heat transfer coefficient between the cell wall and air. The cell experienced a maximum temperature of 56°C when the battery is cooled through natural convection, which is far beyond the optimum battery operating temperature range. According to the infrared image, there is a heat concentration in the middle and top of the cell. The temperature difference between the hottest zone and the edges of the cell reaches almost 5°C which needs special attention to design a cooling system.

2.3.2. Performance of the natural convection and heat pipes on the LTO cell

As is discussed in the last section, natural convection is not sufficient to cool down the cell under the 8C discharging rate. Moreover, it is found that the temperature distribution has more concentration in the middle and top of the cell. Therefore, it needs a smart design to connect the heat pipes to the most critical zone to achieve acceptable cooling performance and temperature uniformity. For this aim, the heat pipes are connected in critical zones (evaporator) with two condensers to maximize the cooling efficiency of the heat pipes [51]. The thermal interface material with thermal conductivity of 8 W/m.K is used to decrease the thermal contact resistance between the heat pipes and the cell. Because of the high thermal conductivity of the heat pipe, the cell heat is rapidly absorbed and transferred to the ambient. It is obvious in Fig. 4 the heat pipes assist heat dissipation with a larger surface area in natural convection. Owing to the increase in the heat dissipation area and high thermal conductivity of heat pipes, the maximum temperature of the cell reaches 46.3°C which is experienced a 17.3% reduction. Moreover, due to heat pipes' effects, the temperature distributions seem to be more uniform. However, the maximum cell temperature is still out of the optimum operating range.

2.3.3. Performance of the PCM assisted heat pipe on the LTO cell

To reach the optimum operating temperature of the Li-ion battery cell, an experimental submerged PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system is built. In this method, the cell embedded with heat pipes is directly submerged in PCM to decrease the cell temperature. Using the submerged method, the thermal contact resistance in current passive or active cooling systems can be eliminated which is lead to

Fig. 3. (a) The location of the thermocouples, (b) the temperature variation, and (c) infrared picture of the LTO cell in natural convection at an initial temperature of 22 °C under the 8C discharging (184 A) rate (Exp: Experimental).

higher cooling performance [52]. The PCM is an organic paraffin wax from Shanghai Tianlan New Material Technology Co., Ltd with a melting temperature of 30 °C, which is ideal and effective for the recommended operating temperature range of the Li-ion cells. Although PCM has a low thermal conductivity, it can compensate with embedded heat pipes. The main parameters of the PCM are mentioned in Table 4.

The PCM assisted heat pipe shows a better performance for cooling of the LTO cell. This is because, throughout the heat exchange, the heat generated within the cell is conducted through the PCM and heat pipes at the same time with almost no thermal contact resistance. The heat transfer and cooling process of the cell can summarize at three main phases as follows: (1) the heat pipes receive the heat from the cell through conduction and transfer it to the PCM. (2) The PCM absorbs and stores the heat generated within the cell and heat pipes through sensible and latent heat storage during the phase change. (3) The PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system dissipates heat to the ambient air. The designed passive cooling system gets benefitted from the relatively high thermal conductivity of heat pipes and with a good heat storage capacity of the PCM. Fig. 5 shows the proposed cooling system which decreased the maximum cell temperature compared to the natural convection and natural convection with heat pipe by 40.7% and 28.3%, respectively.

2.3.4. Maximum temperature distribution of the cell in different thermal management scenarios

The temperature transient response of the cell in different scenarios is plotted in Figs. 5, 4 and 3 under the 8C discharging rate and at the ambient temperature of 22 °C. The heat production and consequent rise in T_1 temperature during the discharging process at natural convection is 54.2 °C at the end of the cycle. A temperature reduction happens for the cell embedded with heat pipes in the same discharge rate and under the same environmental condition. It shows the more efficiency of natural convection using the cooling potential of the heat pipes to control the T_1 temperature under the 46.3 °C. The effectiveness of the passive cooling system can be more obvious in the third scenario. PCM assisted heat pipes cooling system decreases the T_1 temperature to 30.73 °C. It is found that the T_1 temperature decreased by 14.5% and 43.3% for the cell embedded with heat pipe and PCM assisted heat pipe, respectively.

Fig. 4. (a) The picture of the LTO cell embedded with heat pipes, (b) the temperature variation of the LTO cell in natural convection, and (c) the location of heat pipes at an initial temperature of 22 °C at the 8C discharging rate (184 A).

Table 4
The main features of the PCM.

Parameter	value
Melting domain, (°C)	25–32
Max operation temperature, (°C)	210
Thermal conductivity (Solid-Liquid), (W/m.K)	0.25–0.4
Heat storage capacity, (kJ/kg)	220
Density (Solid-Liquid), (kg/lit)	0.8–0.85
Specific heat capacity, (J/kg.K)	2500
PCM container dimensions x,y,z (mm)	265*39*105

3. Simulation

3.1. Battery thermal modeling

COMSOL Multiphysics® has been used to reach the 3D thermal behavior of the cell. The thermal model makes it possible to enhance TMS and use the battery cells in a module/pack. To define the transient thermal distribution inside the cell, an energy balance equation is used. According to this equation, the amount of thermal energy that is generated by the cell to its surrounding is formulated as equation (1). In the present work, the heat generation of the cell is calculated from the ohmic resistance of the cell and the polarization process. Moreover, equation (4) uses for heat generation of the tab domain [53].

$$q_g = R_{bt} \cdot I^2 + R_1 \cdot J_1^2 + R_2 \cdot J_2^2 \tag{3}$$

$$\dot{q} = R_{tab} \cdot I^2 \tag{4}$$

Fig. 5. (a,b) The picture of the PCM assisted heat pipes cooling system, and (c) the temperature variation of the LTO cell at an initial temperature of 22 °C at the 8C discharging (184 A) rate.

$$R_{tab} = \rho' \frac{l}{S} \tag{5}$$

wherein, I and R_{bt} represent the current and ohmic resistance of the cell. Besides, for the tab domains R_{tab} , ρ' , l , S and are the electrical resistance, resistivity, length, and cross-section of the corresponding tab, respectively. Heat transfer from the cell to the surrounding is also calculated as [54]:

$$q_{conv} = h * S (T_{amb} - T) \tag{6}$$

wherein, h and S represent the heat transfer of the coefficient and cross-section area of the cell. Moreover, T and T_{amb} demonstrate the battery and ambient temperature.

3.2. Illustrative equations for PCM

The continuity, momentum, and energy equations for the thermal response of the PCM are classified as follows [30]:

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_r}{r} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = 0 \tag{7}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial r} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} - \frac{u_r}{r^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_r}{\partial z^2} \right) \tag{8}$$

$$\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} + u_z \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial z} = -\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \nu \left(\frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial r} - \frac{u_z}{r^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u_z}{\partial z^2} + g[\beta(T - T_m) - 1] \right) \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{\partial h}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial h}{\partial r} + u_z \frac{\partial h}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho} \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(kr \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) \right] \tag{10}$$

The scaled temperature can be clarified as T_1 as an initial temperature, T_m as a melting temperature T_2 as a final temperature ($T_2 = T_m + \Delta T$). A transition happens between the solid and liquid phases during the implementation of this function within the interval of ΔT . A mushy phase also existed within the interval. It can be seen with mixed properties of the material.

$$T^* \leq T_1 \quad (\text{Solid phase})$$

$$T_1 < T^* < T_2 \quad (\text{Mushy phase}) \tag{11}$$

$$T^* \geq T_2 \quad (\text{Liquid phase})$$

The heat capacity can be mentioned according to the value of phase transition function which depends on the PCM temperature (s : solid; t : transition; l : liquid):

$$C = \begin{cases} c_s & T^* \leq T_1 \\ c_t & T_1 < T^* < T_2 \\ c_l & T^* \geq T_2 \end{cases} \tag{12}$$

Fig. 6. Thermal model validation of the (a) LTO cell under the natural convection, (b) LTO cell embedded with heat pipes under the natural convection, (c) LTO cell embedded with heat pipes and PCM under the 8C discharging rate, and mesh independence of the test setup (Sim: Simulation).

COMSOL using the mentioned heat capacity technique to simulate the melting of the PCM allowing for conductive and convective heat transfer [55]. The heat which is absorbed by the PCM can be evaluated using the following equation:

$$Q_{PCM} = mc_s(T_1 - T_m) + mL + mc_l(T_2 - T_m) \quad (13)$$

where the m is the mass of the PCM. Moreover, the thermal conductivity of the PCM can be expressed as follows:

$$k = \begin{cases} k_s & T^* \leq T_1 \\ \frac{k_s + k_l}{2} & T_1 < T^* < T_2 \\ k_l & T^* \geq T_2 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

3.3. Validation and grid independency of the thermal model for natural convection, heat pipe, and PCM assisted heat pipe

The experimental study on the investigated LTO cell under the effect of natural convection, heat pipe, and PCM assisted heat pipe are considered for validating the adopted numerical results which are conducted with the COMSOL Multiphysics®. The 23Ah LTO cell is discharged with an 8C-rate at an initial temperature of 22 °C for three different scenarios. A total of four thermocouples are connected on the surface of the battery cell. To facilitate the validation and show the accuracy of the simulation, the temperatures of T_1 for all scenarios are compared with the experimental results. As can be seen in Fig. 6, there is an excellent agreement between the simulation and experimental data for three scenarios. The average relative errors for T_1 , for scenarios a, b, and c are 3.3%, 1.2%, and 2.2% respectively within an acceptable error range less than 5% [56]. Moreover, the maximum temperature change of the cell in presence of the PCM-assisted heat pipe is monitored. The computational results are shown in Fig. 6d. It is obvious that the results are grid independent after refining mesh. Consequently, the mesh of elements size of 119742 is selected to prevent the long computational time and solution instability.

3.4. Simulation results and discussion

3.4.1. The natural convection, heat pipe, and PCM assisted heat pipe cooling effect on the cell level

Fig. 7a shows the natural convection temperature contour at a high constant discharge current of 184A from 100% to 0% of SOC. According to Fig. 3a, the localized heat source model has been applied in the cell domain for non-uniform temperature distribution [43]. There is an excellent agreement between simulation and experimental results consistent with Figs. 3a and 6a. The heat pipes are applied with the purpose of maximum cell temperature reduction and uniformity improvement. Fig. 7b and c displays the transient simulation of the cell equipped with heat pipes in natural convection and together with the presence of the PCM. Derived from Fig. 6b and c the transient simulation for the cell embedded with heat pipes and PCM is in good agreement with measured experimental results. It is necessary to note that in the current simulation the heat pipe is substituted by a solid region, and the effective thermal conductivity of components is used in the simulation [27,38,41,43,57].

3.4.2. Thermal and phase change behavior

Fig. 8a displays the pictures taken by the camera during the discharging process which is compared with the temperatures, liquid fraction contours, and thermal images. Along with the images, at the beginning of the discharging process, PCM which is covered the cell, and the heat pipes heated up quickly in conduction mode. The heat pipes rapidly receive and transfer the heat to the cooling medium (PCM). In the initial process of heat transfer, the heat along with the heat pipes wall and cell surface is transferred as conduction within the PCM which is initially in solid-state (100 sec). In this stage, the PCM absorbs the heat in sensible form until it reaches the phase change temperature. Afterward, a thin axial layer of PCM is melted along the heat pipes and the cell surface as shown at 300 sec. According to the shots, as time passes, heat is dissipated into the PCM, and the melting zone increases (446 sec). At this time the PCM absorbs the heat as a latent form and in a constant temperature. It is necessary to note that, the low thermal conductivity of the PCM has been compensated by heat pipes. The phase change and temperature contours have been shown in Fig. 8 b, c. The phase change (solid = 0, liquid = 1) is substantially increased as time passes. The phase change is happening in the mushy zone that is located in the middle of the solid and liquid parts. Fig. 8d shows the thermal images of the temperature distribution of the cell embedded with heat pipes and PCM. Based on the pictures, the cell temperature for 100 sec, 300 sec, and 446 sec reach 26.1 °C, 30.6 °C, and 35.1 °C respectively. The results show that the cell reaches a properly excellent temperature uniformity and maximum temperature using the PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system.

4. Summary and outlook

4.1. Conclusion

The current study experimentally and numerically investigated the cooling performance of the passive TMS for the LTO battery cell under the 8C discharging rate. The results are concluded below:

Fig. 7. (a) Temperature contour of the LTO cell in natural convection, (b) cell embedded with heat pipes, and (c) cell embedded with heat pipes and PCM under the 8C (184A) discharging rate (446 sec).

Fig. 8. (a) Melting up shots, (b, c) temperature and phase change contours, and (d) thermal pictures of the cell equipped with PCM-assisted heat pipe cooling system in 100 sec, 300 sec, and 446 sec under 8C discharging rate.

- The temperature of the cell in presence of natural convection for the initial temperatures of 22 °C in the 8C discharging rate was considered. The experimental results showed that the maximum cell temperature reached 56 °C under the natural convection effect.

- A heat pipe-based natural air cooling system decreased the temperature of the cell to 46.3 °C, which is experienced a 17.3% reduction in maximum cell temperature.
- Using the PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system, the maximum cell temperature reached 33.2 °C, which experienced a 40.7% reduction.
- The CFD model for different cooling strategies was validated with the experimental results and attained an acceptable agreement.
- The thermal images, phase change process, and temperature distribution contours have been considered in 100 sec, 300 sec, and 466 sec for the PCM assisted heat pipe cooling system.

4.2. Future work

The advantages of using the submerged cooling system on different charge-discharge scenarios, for other Li-ion cell chemistries can be studied. Moreover, the effect of the studied cooling system can be investigated at the module/pack level.

Credit author statement

Hamidreza Behi: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Experiment, Validation, Investigation, Data curation, Writing - original draft., **Danial Karimi:** Software, Investigation, Validation., **Foad Heidari Gandoman:** Writing - review & editing., **Mohsen Akbarzadeh:** Writing - review & editing. **Sahar Khaleghi:** Writing - review & editing. **Theodoros Kalogiannis:** Writing - review & editing. **Md Sazzad Hosen:** Writing, Data curation, Visualization., **Joris Jaguemont:** Methodology, Writing - review & editing., **Joeri Van Mierlo:** Review & editing., **Maitane Berecibar:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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